

ASSESSMENT OF PREVALENCE AND PHENOMENOLOGY OF MENTAL
COMPULSIONS IN PATIENTS WITH OBSESSIVE-COMPULSIVE DISORDER: A
CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University), VIJAYAPURA

In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of

MD in Psychiatry

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DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “**Assessment of Prevalence and Phenomenology of mental compulsions in patients with Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder: A cross-sectional study**” is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of **Dr SANTOSH RAMDURG**, Professor and Head, Department of Psychiatry, at BLDE (Deemed to be University) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS USED

SR. NO.	ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
01.	OCD	Obsessive Compulsive Disorder
02.	OCRDs	Obsessive Compulsive and Related Disorders
03.	CBT	Cognitive Behavioural Therapy
04.	ERP	Exposure Response Prevention
05.	Y-BOCS	Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale
06.	DY-BOCS	Dimensional Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale
07.	GAF	Global Assessment of Functioning
08.	MINI	Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview
09.	ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases 10 th edition
10.	DSM-IV	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders IVth edition
11.	DSM V	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders Vth edition
12.	MINI	Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview
13.	SCID	Structured Clinical Interview for DSM
14.	GAD	Generalised Anxiety Disorder

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND : Obsessive Compulsive Disorder (OCD) is a significant mental condition due to its prevalence and disability it causes, is characterised by presence of obsessions and compulsions. OCD is more common in females than males in epidemiological studies. Mental rituals are defined as compulsions with no overt behavioral or motoric symptoms like repeating certain words or phrases in the mind. The exact prevalence of mental compulsions could be underestimated due to measurement issues using Y-BOCS and its clinical characteristics. Most commonly they are found to occur following religious / sexual, harm or aggressive obsessions. They are more chronic and severe form of OCD and response poorly to Cognitive Behavioural Therapy. Given the relatively high prevalence of mental compulsion, along with scant study on their phenomenology and clinical correlations, as well as the potentially crucial repercussions for course and treatment, greater research is necessary.

METHODOLOGY: This cross-sectional study was carried out after taking institutional Ethical committee clearance of BLDE(DU) Shri B.M Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura. People in the age group of 10 to 60 years with a diagnosis of obsessive compulsive disorder were assessed for symptom profile using DY-BOCS and a mental compulsions checklist. Severity of the disease was assessed using Y-BOCS severity rating scale and impact of OCD on individual's life was assessed by using Global Assessment of Functioning. Additionally, MINI was used to assess comorbid psychiatric illness.

RESULTS: In a sample of 80 participants with Obsessive- Compulsive Disorder, the overall point prevalence of mental compulsions in patients with Obsessive-compulsive disorder was 53.75% (n=43). Most of these patients had behavioural compulsions as well. Mental compulsions were more common in males 58.13% (n=25) than in females 41.87% (n=18). Among 43 patients having mental compulsions, obsessions about sacrilege and blasphemy were most common (35%) followed by obsessions related to symmetry (32%). The most common mental compulsions were undoing "bad" thoughts with "good" thoughts (51%) followed by praying (40%) and reassuring themselves (32%). Overall, psychiatric comorbidity was more common in the participants with mental compulsions.

Conclusions : Mental compulsions were present in more than half of the study sample. They were most common following religious, symmetry and harm related obsessions. Most of the patients had multiple mental compulsions. Most common types were undoing bad thoughts

with good thoughts followed by praying, reassuring themselves and repeating phrases or mantras. Patients with mental compulsions had higher comorbid psychiatric illness than patients without mental compulsions. More than half of the sample had comorbid psychiatric illness

KEYWORD : Obsessive compulsive disorder, mental compulsions, sacrilegious obsessions, comorbidities in OCD, Y-BOCS, mental replacing, mental checking

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is a significant mental health condition due to its prevalence, the disability it causes, and its role as a primary example within the category of obsessive-compulsive and related disorders. As per ICD-11, Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is defined by the presence of obsessions and compulsions. Obsessions are repetitive and persistent thoughts, images, impulses or urges that are intrusive or unwanted and are commonly associated with anxiety. Compulsions are repetitive behaviours, including repetitive mental acts that the individual feels driven to perform in response to an obsession, according to rigid rules, or to achieve a sense of 'completeness' [1]. Children may struggle to define or describe obsessions, but most adults recognize both obsessions and compulsions. According to cognitive-behavioural theories, obsessions often lead to worry or discomfort. Compulsions are performed in response to these obsessions to relieve the anxiety. However, some data suggests that compulsive behaviour is primary, with obsessions occurring as a post-hoc justification of these behaviours, albeit this view warrants further investigation [2]. The majority of OCD patients are aware of their symptoms, understand that they are excessive, and wish to have more control over them [3].

Figure 1 Classification of OCRDs

OCD was always thought to be rather rare, but recent studies have shown that it is one of the most common mental diseases, contributing significantly to the worldwide disease burden [4].

According to the most recent surveys in European and North American countries, the lifetime prevalence of OCD is between 2-3% [5,6,7]. The figures vary by region. An epidemiologic study conducted in India revealed a lifetime prevalence of 0.6%, which is significantly lower than in Western countries [8]. A comparable lower rate of 0.6-0.9% was observed in Taiwanese research. The explanation for the lesser incidence in different nations is yet unclear.

In the population, OCD is more common in girls than in males, although in clinical samples, the gender ratio is often fairly even. Likewise, OCD impacts individuals across all socioeconomic classes and is prevalent in low-, middle-, and high-income countries. [9,10].

OCD typically develops early in life and lasts for an extended period. In the National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) study, nearly 25% of boys experienced onset before age ten. Females typically develop OCD symptoms throughout adolescence, while some may have them during the peripartum or postpartum period [11].

Age is the most significant sociodemographic predictor of lifelong OCD, which is consistent with the disorder's early development. OCD is most common in people aged 18 to 29, however it can also affect people beyond the age of 30 [10]. Longitudinal clinical and community studies have revealed that OCD symptoms can endure for decades, yet a significant portion of persons can experience remission. [12]

The World Health Organization and Global Burden of Disease Study identify OCD as one of the most devastating noncommunicable disorders worldwide. Years lost to disability and all-cause death are similar to schizophrenia and higher than many neurologic disorders, including epilepsy. Beyond the direct costs of OCD treatment and the increased use of healthcare services due to comorbidities or related health conditions, OCD incurs significant indirect costs on society and national economies. These include reduced productivity (with over 30% of individuals with OCD being underemployed or unemployed), lower income, and a high number of missed workdays [13,14]. Furthermore, OCD is associated with an increased caregiver burden, which diminishes productivity, functioning, and quality of life, particularly for parents and partners of individuals with OCD [15].

Twin studies have illuminated the roles of genetic and environmental factors in OCD. A meta-analysis of these studies found that about 40% of the variation in obsessive-compulsive symptoms can be attributed to additive genetic effects, while non-shared environmental factors account for roughly 51% of the variance. Furthermore, early research indicates that gene-environment interactions may play a role in the development of OCD, and that general etiological factors, such as those influencing negative emotionality, may shape obsessive-compulsive symptoms [16]. Certain subtypes of OCD, such as early-onset OCD with tics, might exhibit higher heritability compared to others [17].

Research has focused on specific genes that might contribute to OCD, particularly those involved in the serotonin and dopamine systems. Some studies have identified associations between OCD and polymorphisms in genes such as the serotonin transporter gene (SLC6A4) and the dopamine receptor gene (DRD4). [18,19]

Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) have been used to identify common genetic variants associated with OCD. These studies scan the genome for small variations that occur more frequently in people with OCD compared to those without the disorder. Some variants near genes involved in glutamate signalling, such as SLC1A1, have been implicated in OCD. [20]

While genetics play a significant role, environmental factors also contribute to the development of OCD. Studies suggest that genetic predispositions can interact with environmental triggers (such as stress or trauma) to increase the risk of OCD. [18,19]

Five types of obsessions have been identified: doubts (60-70%), obsessive thinking (30-50%), obsessive fears (25-40%), obsessive impulses (10-15%) and obsessive images (4-5%). Compulsive acts could be classified into two types yielding and controlling compulsions based on whether they give expression to underlying obsession or not. The content of obsession could be classified in six broad categories as relating to: dirt and contamination, aggression or harm, inanimate-impersonal themes that included symmetry, religion, and sexual matters [21].

Common obsessions and compulsions in OCD patients include concerns about dirt and contamination often leading to ritualised washing or cleaning, concerns about harm to self or others with repeated checking if they had done the same, intrusive aggressive or sexual

thoughts with mental rituals, and concerns about symmetry with things needing to be perfect or repeated counting [22,23]. These symptom characteristics have been recorded all over the world, demonstrating that OCD is an illness that appears to be universal. Nonetheless, OCD can manifest as a variety of less prevalent symptoms, such as scrupulosity, obsessional jealousy, and musical obsessions [24,25]. Another significant aspect of OCD is avoidance; people may limit their activities in order to avoid triggering obsessions (3). Although sociocultural factors can undoubtedly influence the phenomenology of obsessive-compulsive symptoms, particularly the thought content of the obsessions, there is also a significant uniformity of OCD symptoms over the world [26].

Men were more likely to have sexual obsessions, hoarding, repetitive rituals, and need-to-touch compulsions, whereas women reported compulsive washing. Compulsions manifest as an overt act or behavior that may be witnessed by others, such as repeated hand washing or checking to see if the door is locked.

Mental rituals are defined as compulsions with no overt behavioral or motoric symptoms. Examples include repeating certain words or phrases in the mind, praying, counting words, letters or numbers, mental checking, replacing an obsession with a different image or a word, and neutralizing disturbing mental pictures. The definition and diagnostic criteria for OCD was updated in DSM -IV and it included mental rituals as well which shows how clinically importance and the chronicity of this symptom presentation [27]. Patients with mental compulsions have been earlier described under numerous titles, including ruminators, neutralizers, and possibly misinterpreted as "pure obsessives". [28]

Despite the inclusion of mental rituals in the DSM-IV diagnostic criteria, research into the phenomenology and clinical correlates of this symptom presentation is surprisingly limited. The scant data available suggests that mental rituals are a prevalent compulsion in people with OCD, with a prevalence of 9.8 to 25% in individuals with OCD, with some studies estimating a prevalence up to 60% of patients [29,30].

The exact prevalence of mental compulsions could be underestimated due to multitude of reasons. For example, Abramowitz and colleagues [30] highlight measurement issues and incomplete symptom analysis in studies using the Yale-Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) and Symptom Checklist [31,32]. These tools include mental rituals and other items in the "miscellaneous compulsions" category. Often, this category is either removed

from analyses or treated as a single item, which hinders the identification of important patterns related to mental rituals. Aside from measuring difficulties, clinical considerations may influence reporting. Limited study has discovered that sexual, repulsive, aggressive, or blasphemous obsessions are common companions of mental rituals [33]. The patient may have mental compulsions such as silently repeating words or phrases in their head, praying, mentally counting till they feel "right," mentally checking, replaying memories or conversations, and replacing "bad" thoughts with "good" emotions. Patients can carry out these mental compulsions easily and in any place; others cannot perceive them, making them more difficult to resist and manage. When the compulsions are covert or stigmatizing, identifying OCD becomes more challenging. People may just notice that the individual appears distracted, anxious, or reacts slowly to inquiries. They wouldn't be able to see the person mentally praying, attempting to convince themselves that a specific behavior is safe, or mentally replacing unsuitable sexual notions with "safe" or "proper" ones [34]. As a result, patients with OCD frequently hide their intrusive thoughts or pictures because they believe they are too humiliating. Researchers believe that the emotional and moral significance of the content of these intrusive thoughts may raise reluctance to report and confront them in treatment. People may also be reluctant to share the content of their thoughts with a health practitioner for fear of being misunderstood [35]. As a result, the prevalence of mental rituals in clinical OCD populations may be underestimated due to patients' reluctance to discuss the often related offensive obsessions.

Perhaps more crucially, studies indicate that people who present with mental compulsions as their primary compulsion face distinct obstacles in the management. Mental compulsions may act as a sort of cognitive avoidance during exposure and response prevention. This makes the patient unable to habituate to these anxiety-provoking stimuli in both therapy and daily life [36]. Some believe that OCD patients with mental compulsions have a poor response to standard OCD treatments such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and exposure and ritual prevention (ERP), as there is no overt behaviour to target and change. Although, evidence from recent studies is mixed. Several investigations have shown that OCD patients with obsessions but no overt compulsions do not respond to ERP or medication [37]. A small number of studies and case reports have found that OCD patients with mental compulsions show no different response than those without mental compulsions. [30,38], whereas others have shown preliminary

efficacy in the treatment of mental compulsions with interventions tailored to this clinical presentation [39,40].

Given the relatively high prevalence of mental compulsion, along with scant study on their phenomenology and clinical correlations, as well as the potentially crucial repercussions for course and treatment, greater research is necessary.

Comorbidities are seen with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) across the lifespan. The most common are mood disorders, anxiety disorders, impulse control disorders, substance use disorders and personality disorders. Tic disorders and other OCRDs also commonly cooccur with OCD [10].

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Studies explicitly examining mental compulsions in individuals diagnosed with obsessive compulsive disorder are scarce. Studies discuss the prevalence of mental compulsions, but there are few that address their phenomenology. There is a dearth of research on the phenomenology and clinical correlates of mental compulsions in OCD specifically from India, which makes this study somewhat unique.

Three concerns were looked at during the DSM IV field trial, which was conducted to update the DSM-III-R criteria for obsessive-compulsive disorder. 1) The patient's perception of the symptoms as excessive or illogical; 2) The existence of mental compulsive behaviours in addition to behavioural ones; and 3) ICD-10 subtypes. The findings showed that the majority of patients had both behavioural and mental compulsions, and that the majority were unsure of whether their obsessive-compulsive symptoms were excessive or unjustified. Only 0.2% of respondents reported having mental compulsions without behavioural compulsions, compared to 79.5% who reported having both mental and behavioural compulsions. Moreover, it demonstrated that 80.7% of the mental rituals and 90.4% of the core behavioural rituals had a functional relationship with obsessions. The study came to the conclusion that mental rituals should be included in the description of compulsions and that the DSM-III-R need for insight should be lessened in the DSM-IV. However, neither the common categories of mental compulsions nor their clinical correlations were discussed in this study. [29].

Despite the enhanced attention on mental compulsions in DSM-IV, and DSM-V, and its mention in ICD-11, research on the phenomenology and clinical consequences of this symptom presentation remains surprisingly sparse. The scant information that is currently available indicates that mental routines are a common worry for people with OCD; prevalence in clinical settings ranges from 9.8% to 25%, with some studies reporting as high as 60%.

Since most studies use one of the most standard tools for assessing OCD, the Yale-Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) and Symptom Checklist, which includes mental compulsions in the "miscellaneous compulsions" category, so due to measurement problems and incomplete analysis the exact prevalence of the mental compulsions could not be assessed.

The exclusion of this category from data analysis impedes the identification of possible important clinical correlates associated with mental compulsions.

In addition to measurement difficulties, certain clinical aspects of mental compulsions may also effect reporting. Available research has found that sexual, abhorrent, aggression, or blasphemous obsessions are common to mental compulsions, which could be embarrassing for patients and make them reluctant to report these and associated compulsions and seek help which underestimates the prevalence of mental compulsions.

To adequately assess mental compulsions, Abramowitz et al in 2003 conducted 2 studies in a large sample of 132 patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder. 1st study was undertaken to assess the symptom profile of the patients with OCD and it also assessed the mental compulsions. Five patient subgroups were seen: aggression or harm, dirt and contamination, hoarding, unacceptable thoughts, and symmetry. Mental compulsions were more common secondary to religious or blasphemous, harm or aggression, and sexual obsessions. The second study, which examined the responsiveness of the identified symptom profiles to cognitive behavioural therapy, discovered that patients with hoarding obsessions and compulsions performed worse than other symptom domains. [30].

A longitudinal study conducted by Nicholas J. Sibrava et al. in 2011 showed that Of 225 study participants mental compulsions were the primary compulsion for 12.9% of the sample. An additional 20.4% had mental compulsions as a current symptom, while 16% reported having them in the past. Only 3.4% of those with primary mental compulsions had no other compulsive symptoms. Of the participants who endorsed mental compulsions as primary compulsions, they were most commonly secondary to harm related obsessions (e.g., fear of harming self/other, being responsible for something bad happening) and was seen in 41.4% of individuals with mental compulsions. Fears of offending God and sacrilegious thoughts (20.7%) was the second most common obsession. Most common type of mental compulsion seen was praying. It was seen in 48.3% of the individuals with mental compulsions. This was followed by undoing bad thoughts with good thoughts. Primary mental compulsions were associated with greater clinical severity, lower quality of life at enrolment, and a more chronic course of illness. There were no significant differences in treatment utilization (psychotherapy or pharmacotherapy) between

those with and without primary mental rituals, suggesting that treatment received does not explain the chronicity differences. The findings suggest that mental rituals are a more severe and chronic form of OCD. There is a need for early detection and improved interventions specifically targeting mental rituals to prevent poorer long-term outcomes and lower quality of life. These findings highlight the unique challenges and significant impact of mental rituals in OCD, emphasizing the importance of addressing this symptom subtype in both clinical practice and research [41].

In 2014 Roseli G. Shavitt et al. [42] conducted a multicentric study to study the phenomenology of OCD and to contribute to the revision of diagnostic criteria for OCD and showed that 56.7% of patients with OCD had mental compulsions. A previous DSM-IV field trial reported a higher prevalence (79.5%) due to a different assessment approach. The study used the Dimensional Yale-Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (DY-BOCS) to assess mental compulsions within each symptom dimension. This approach contrasts with the DSM-IV field trial, which added specific items to capture mental compulsions comprehensively. Both the studies found that mental compulsions are common in individuals with OCD and almost always occur alongside behavioral compulsions. In the study, no participants had mental compulsions without behavioral compulsions. In contrast, the DSM-IV trial found this in only 0.2% of cases. Mental compulsions were most common in the symmetry/ordering/arranging (28.2%), aggression (27.0%), and sexual/religious dimensions (24.7%). They were less common in contamination (16.6%) and miscellaneous dimensions (13.2%), and least common in the hoarding dimension (8.3%). The common types of mental compulsions included organizing objects mentally, checking lists of tasks mentally, thinking "good" thoughts to remove "bad" aggressive thoughts, thinking good thoughts after blasphemous thoughts, saying prayers repeatedly.

In 2017, T.S. Jaisoorya and colleagues [43] conducted a study examining the prevalence of OCD and subthreshold OCD among 5784 college students aged 18-25 in Ernakulam, Kerala, India. Using self-administered assessment they found that OCD had a point prevalence of 3.3% (3.5% in males and 3.2% in females). Additionally, 8.5% of students (9.9% males, 7.7% females) met criteria for subthreshold OCD. Among those with OCD, the most common symptoms were taboo thoughts (67.1%) and mental rituals (57.4%). Students with OCD had

higher rates of comorbid psychiatric disorders, particularly depression and anxiety disorders, compared to those without OCD. SOCD was also associated with increased rates of comorbid psychiatric disorders, though to a lesser extent than full OCD. Both OCD and SOCD were associated with significant functional impairment, including academic difficulties and interpersonal problems. The severity of impairment was greater in students with OCD compared to those with SOCD. The study highlights that OCD and SOCD are prevalent among college students in Kerala, India, and are associated with considerable comorbidities and functional impairment. The findings suggest the need for increased awareness, early identification, and intervention for OCD and SOCD in this population.

In 2023, Ferrão JVB [44] conducted a study to investigate the prevalence and psychological associations of mental rituals (MR). The study compared 519 patients exhibiting mental rituals to 447 patients without MR, examining sociodemographic factors, severity of obsessive-compulsive symptoms, psychiatric comorbidities, sensory phenomena, suicidality, and insight. The findings revealed that 51.8% of the sample currently experienced MR, while 55.4% had experienced them at some point in their lives. Through multiple logistic regression analysis, the study identified that the absence of sensory phenomena and lifetime suicidal thoughts were the primary clinical factors independently linked with current MR among OCD patients.

In 2021, Sharma et al. [45] published a comprehensive review and meta-analysis on the prevalence of comorbidities in patients with OCD during their lifespan. They conducted a comprehensive search of four electronic databases (PubMed, EMBASE, SCOPUS, and PsycINFO) using predetermined search criteria, encompassing publications published between 1979 and 2020. The review included 91 studies with a collective sample size exceeding 15,000 individuals.

The findings indicated that the pooled prevalence of any psychiatric disorder among OCD patients was 69.3%. Specifically, the pooled prevalence rates were 47.7% for any mood disorder, 32.2% for anxiety disorders, 16.2% for neurodevelopmental disorders, 13.7% for other obsessive-compulsive and related disorders (OCRDs), and 34.9% for personality disorders.

AIM

To study the prevalence, phenomenology and severity of mental compulsions in patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the types and severity of mental compulsions in study participants.
2. To assess associated comorbid psychiatric illnesses

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

We carried out a Cross-sectional, single-centre, interview-based study of total 80 study participants who were diagnosed to have Obsessive – Compulsive Disorder as per ICD-11, at Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura from August 2022 to February 2024.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients with a primary diagnosis of OCD as per ICD 11 who presented to the Psychiatry Department.
2. Age group 10-60 years

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients with schizophrenia or any other psychotic illness.
2. Having an intellectual disability

SAMPLE SIZE

With the Anticipated Proportion of OCD at 0.6% [Y. C. Janardhan Reddy, Naren P. Rao, Sumant Khanna An overview of Indian research in obsessive-compulsive disorder Indian J Psychiatry. 2010 Jan; 52(Suppl 1): S200-S209.], the study would require a sample size of 80 to achieve a power of 80%, and two-sided p-value of 0.05 with effect size 0.094 using G* power software 3.1.9.7.

METHOD

Informed consent was taken from the patients. In the case of patients aged <18 years, informed consent was taken from parents/guardians. Confidentiality was upheld during the interview. Before starting the interview, adequate time was spent with each patient to establish a good rapport. Prior approval from the ethics committee of our institution (Institutional Review Board) was taken. The interview was conducted in the participants' native language (Kannada or Hindi). Participants' replies were recorded on a proforma that included demographic information such as their initials, age, religion, residence, occupation, education, age of onset of symptoms, and age at first visit to the hospital for the same.

Interview of every participant was taken for diagnosis of Obsessive Compulsive Disorder using the ICD (International Classification of disease) 11th revision (ICD 11).

Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) (Goodman et al., 1989) (31,32) was applied to look for the severity of OCD symptoms utilizing ten questions, five addressing obsessions and five addressing compulsions, about the amount of time spent per day with symptoms, interference due to the symptoms, distress caused by the symptoms, resistance and control over symptoms. Individual scores range from 0 to 4 (total score 0-40), with the higher score meaning greater severity.

0-13: mild symptoms

14-25: moderate symptoms

26-34: moderate-severe symptoms

35-40: severe symptoms

For the total scale, the mean reliability is 0.866 for coefficients alpha and 0.848 for test-retest correlations.

Dimensional Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale Symptom Checklist (DYBOCS) (Rosario-Campos et al., 2006) [46] was applied to evaluate OCD symptoms according to eight dimensions: (1) obsessions about harm and related compulsions (2) sexual/religious obsessions and related compulsions, (3) symmetry/ordering/counting/doing and redoing things, (4) contamination worries and cleaning compulsions, (5) collecting and hoarding (6)

somatic obsessions and compulsions (7) miscellaneous obsessions and compulsions (8) other OC spectrum obsessions and compulsions. Provides both obsessions and compulsions , both, behavioural and mental, within each dimension. DY-BOCS was used instead of the Y-BOCS symptom checklist as it asks about mental compulsions inside each symptom dimension. It has excellent internal consistency across the time, distress and interference domains for each dimension. The expert raters on the DY-BOCS exhibited outstanding interrater reliability. For every DY-BOCS component score, the intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) were more than 0.98. For the Aggressive, Sexual/Religious, Symmetry, Contamination, Hoarding, and Miscellaneous aspects, Cronbach's alpha is 0.94, 0.95, and 0.96. The DY-BOCS total global severity score has convergent validity, as evidenced by the strong connection (Pearson $r = 0.82$, $P < 0.0001$) between its total global score and the Y-BOCS total score.

The effect of OCD on a patient's life was evaluated using the Global Assessment of Functioning (GAF). It is divided into ten parts. These are called as anchor points. A patient will be able to manage everyday tasks better if he receives a higher score. The intraclass correlation between two raters, which measures inter-rater reliability, is 0.89 [47].

Comorbidities were assessed via clinical interview.

A MENTAL COMPULSIONS CHECKLIST was made based on the most common types of mental compulsions observed and included

- Praying
- Undoing bad thoughts with good thoughts
- Repeating phrases/mantras
- Reassuring themselves
- Organizing objects mentally or Mental checking
- Counting/numbers mentally
- Others

The severity of mental compulsions was assessed based on time spent on performing mental compulsions as per the Y-BOCS and divided into mild, moderate, moderate-severe and severe if they spent less than 1 hour per day, 1-3 hours, 3-8 hours and more than 8 hours per day respectively.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data obtained was entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS.

Results were presented as Mean \pm SD, Median and Inter quartile range, Frequency, percentages and diagrams.

RESULTS

RESULTS

FIG 1. SAMPLE

Out of 83 patients studied during the time frame, 80 were included in the final analysis. Out of 80 patients, 51.2% (N=41) were females and 48.8% (n=39) were males. 58.75% (n=47) of the sample was aged less than 30 years, 60% (n=48) of the sample had studied above high school and 56.3% (n=45) were married. The sociodemographic profile of the final sample is given in Table 1.

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE		
<20	9	11.3
20-29	38	47.5
30-39	23	28.7
40-49	7	8.8
50-59	3	3.8
SEX		
MALE	39	48.8
FEMALE	41	51.2
EDUCATION		
ILLITERATE	9	11.3
UPTO MIDDLE SCHOOL	3	3.8
MIDDLE TO HIGH SCHOOL	20	25.0
PRECOLLEGE	18	22.5
GRADUATE	30	37.5
OCCUPATION		
STUDENT	23	28.7
HOUSEWIFE	19	23.8
SERVICE	11	13.8
FARMER	8	10.0
UNEMPLOYED	8	10.0
BUSINESS	6	7.5
DAILY WAGE WORKER	5	6.3
MARITAL STATUS		
UNMARRIED	33	41.3
MARRIED	45	56.3
DIVORCED/WIDOWED	2	2.6
RELIGION		
HINDU	53	66.3
MUSLIM	27	33.8

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS		
LSES	36	45.0
LMSES	27	33.8
USES	17	21.3

Table 1. Sociodemographic profile

The mean age of onset of symptoms was 22.32 years (SD=5.6). The mean age of onset of symptoms in males was 21.2 years (SD=4.4) and in females was 23.4 years (SD=6.3).

TYPES OF OBSESSIONS AND COMPULSIONS

Out of 80 participants, 41.25% (n=33) had a single type of obsession and compulsion while 58.75% (n=47) had multiple types of obsessions and compulsions. Most common obsessions and compulsions were in dimension of dirt and contamination i.e 48.75% (n=39) followed by symmetry – 27.5% (n=22), harm – 21.25% (n=17), religious – 21.25% (n=17) and sexual – 20% (n=16). Types of obsessions and compulsions are given in Fig 2. And Fig 3 respectively.

Out of 41 females, the most common obsessions and compulsions were in the dimension of dirt and contamination 56.09 (n=23) followed by symmetry 29.26% (n=12), harm 19.51% (n=8), miscellaneous compulsions 19.51% (n=8). Less commonly observed were religious 9.75% (n=4), sexual 7.31% (n=3), OCRDs 7.31% (n=3) and collecting 2.43% (n=1).

Out of 39 males, the most common obsessions and compulsions were for dirt and contamination 41.02% (n=16) followed by religious 33.3% (n=13), sexual 33.3% (n=13), symmetry 25.6% (n=10). Less common were somatic 7.69% (n=3) and miscellaneous obsessions 5.12% (n=2)

Most patients had obsessions followed by compulsion in the same dimension. However, only 27.5% (n=22) participants had obsessions related to symmetry while 35% (n=28) participants had compulsions related to the symmetry sub-domain of DYBOCS and only 5% (n=4)

participants had miscellaneous obsessions while 13.75% (n=11) had miscellaneous compulsions.

CONTENT OF OBSESSIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
HARM/ AGGRESSION	17	21.25
SEXUAL	16	20
RELIGIOUS	17	21.25
SYMMETRY	22	27.5
DIRT AND CONTAMINATION	39	48.75
COLLECTING AND HOARDING	1	1.25
SOMATIC	3	3.75
MISCELLANEOUS	4	5.0
OCRDS	3	3.75

Table 2. Content of obsessions

Fig 2. Content of obsessions

CONTENT OF COMPULSIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
HARM/ AGGRESSIVE	17	21.25
SEXUAL	16	20
RELIGIOUS	17	21.25
SYMMETRY	28	35
DIRT AND CONTAMINATION	39	48.75
COLLECTING AND HOARDING	1	1.25
SOMATIC	3	3.75
MISCELLANEOUS	11	1.25
OCRDS	3	3.75

Table 3. Content of compulsions.

Fig. 3 Content of compulsions

SEVERITY OF THE DISORDER

Most participants (73.75%) had moderate to moderate-severe illness as per the YBOCS severity rating scale.

SEVERITY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MILD	20	25.0
MODERATE	40	50.0
MODERATE-SEVERE	19	23.75
SEVERE	1	1.25
TOTAL	80	100

Table 4. Severity of OCD

PREVALENCE OF MENTAL COMPULSIONS

The overall point prevalence of mental compulsions in patients with Obsessive-compulsive disorder was 53.75% (n=43). Most of these patients had behavioural compulsions as well.

Mental compulsions were more common in males 58.13% (n=25) than in females 41.87% (n=18).

The prevalence of mental compulsions is given in Table 3.

Most participants endorsed multiple compulsions, i.e. about 70% of participants had more than 1 mental compulsion. Fig 5

10 out of 80 patients i.e. 12.5% had mental compulsions as a primary compulsion in one of the domains. Out of 10, 5 had primary mental compulsions for harm obsessions, and 5 had primary mental compulsions for religious and sexual obsessions. Only 1 patient had only mental compulsions and no behavioural compulsion and it was secondary to obsession that she might harm someone without meaning to harm them or blurt insults to someone and had mental compulsions in the form of replacing bad thoughts with good thoughts and reassuring herself.

Fig 4 Types of compulsions

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
OVERALL	43	53.75
SEX		
MALE	25	58.13
FEMALE	18	41.87
AGE		
<20	4	9.30
20-29	23	53.48
30-39	14	32.55
40-49	2	4.65
EDUCATION		
ILLITERATE	6	13.95
UPTO MIDDLE SCHOOL	1	2.32
MIDDLE TO HIGH SCHOOL	9	20.93
PRECOLLEGE	10	23.25
COLLEGE	17	39.53
OCCUPATION		
STUDENT	11	25.58
HOUSEWIFE	8	18.60
SERVICE	6	13.95
FARMER	6	13.95
UNEMPLOYED	3	6.97
BUSINESS	4	9.30
DAILY WAGE WORKER	5	11.62
MARITAL STATUS		
MARRIED	27	62.79
UNMARRIED	14	32.55
DIVORCED/WIDOWED	2	4.65
RELIGION		
HINDU	30	69.76
MUSLIM	13	30.23

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS		
LSES	21	48.83
LMSES	11	25.58
UMSES	11	25.58

Table 5. Prevalence of mental compulsions

Fig 5. Number of mental compulsions.

Types of mental compulsions.

Among 43 patients having mental compulsions, obsessions about sacrilege and blasphemy were most common (35%) followed by obsessions related to symmetry (32%). The most common mental compulsions were undoing “bad” thoughts with “good” thoughts (51%) followed by praying (40%) and reassuring themselves (32%). Fig 6

Fig 6. Types of mental compulsions

Fig 7. Mental compulsions in males

Fig 8. Mental compulsions in females

Fig 9 Content of obsessions

Most commonly mental compulsions were associated with religious obsessions, 88% of patients with religious obsessions had mental compulsion. While 70.6 % of patients with harm obsessions, 68.75% of patients with sexual obsessions, 50% of patients with symmetry obsessions, and only 5% of patients with dirt and contamination obsessions.

SEVERITY OF MENTAL COMPULSIONS

SEVERITY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MILD	11	25.58
MODERATE	14	32.55
MODERATE-SEVERE	17	39.53
SEVERE	1	2.32

Table 6. Severity of mental compulsions

Most of the patients endorsing mental compulsions spent 3-8 hours of the day time performing these compulsions i.e. 39.5%. 32.5% spent 1-3 hours per day while 25.5% spent less than 1 hour per day performing these mental compulsions.

Only 1 participant spent more than 8 hours performing mental compulsions.

Most of the patients did not try to resist these compulsions and gave in to these compulsions and were not deemed unnecessary.

Fig 10. Global assessment of functioning

Lower scores indicate poorer functioning. 30% of patients with mental compulsions had a score of 61-70 suggesting mild impairment while 27.9 % had a score of 51-60 suggesting moderate impairment and 25.5% had a score of 71-80 suggesting severe impairment. Only 4.6 % of participants with mental compulsions had major impairment in socio-occupational functioning

COMORBIDITIES.

Out of 80 patients, 47 (58.75%) patients had a comorbid psychiatric illness and out of 43 patients with mental compulsions 26 (60.46%) patients had any comorbid psychiatric illness. Overall, psychiatric comorbidity was more common in the participants with mental compulsions. 7.5 % of patients also reported suicidal ideations

Fig 11. Comorbidities associated with OCD.

DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION

OCD was slightly more common in females than males in our study and it was present in all socioeconomic classes which is in accordance with prior epidemiological studies. A study of the epidemiology of Obsessive–Compulsive Disorder in National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) Study by Ruscio AM, Stein DJ et al in 2008 it was seen that OCD was more common in females than males [10].

In our study, the mean age of onset of OCD was 22.3 years. OCD in females had a later onset than the males. Similar results were seen in National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) study which found that the odd of onset were highest from 18-29 years of age.

In a retrospective chart review by Agarwal AK et al in 2022, using case records of patients diagnosed with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) it was seen that the age of onset of the illness was in the late 20s [48].

In a meta-analysis of OCD prevalence worldwide by Fawcett et al in 2020 [49] which included 34 studies, it was found that women are more likely to experience OCD in their lifetime than men. The study also found a lifetime prevalence of 1.5% in women compared with 1.0% in men. Additionally, compared to older adults, younger adults appear to have a higher lifetime risk of developing OCD, according to the study.

Mathes BM et al. [50] conducted a review in 2019 focusing on recent studies exploring gender variations in OCD. The review revealed that OCD appears to be more prevalent among males during childhood, but the prevalence shifts to females during adolescence and adulthood. Additionally, males generally report an earlier age when OCD symptoms first appear compared to females.

Jaisoorya *et al.* [51] in 2008 examined gender differences in OCD. The average age of onset for OCD was earlier in males compared to females. Males and females exhibited different predominant OCD symptoms. Males more commonly reported aggressive, sexual, and religious obsessions. Females tended to have more contamination obsessions and cleaning compulsions.

In 2007, Fontenelle LF et al. [9] carried out a qualitative comprehensive review of the literature, looking at studies on the genetic, environmental, and demographic risk variables linked to the start of OCD in epidemiological studies. Their review indicated that a substantial number of studies suggest late adolescence as a period of increased vulnerability for developing OCD. Furthermore, OCD was found to predominantly affect males during adolescence and females during adulthood.

CONTENT OF OBSESSIONS AND COMPULSIONS

In our study, 41.25% of participants had obsessions and compulsions in a single domain and 58.75% in multiple domains. The most common symptoms were in the domain of dirt and contamination (48.25%) followed by symmetry (27.5%), harm and religious (21.25%) each and sexual (20%). The most common type of obsessions and compulsions in males were dirt and contamination followed by religious, sexual and symmetry. The most common types of obsessions and compulsions in females were dirt and contamination, followed by symmetry, harm and miscellaneous compulsions. Most of the patients had a compulsion following an obsession. However, only 27.5% (n=22) participants had obsessions related to symmetry while 35% (n=28) participants had compulsions related to symmetry. These compulsions "need to touch, tap or rub things" or "need to repeat routine activities" were not associated with an obsession. These patients could have a preceding sensory phenomenon, which was not assessed in this study. The results of our study are in line with the studies of the phenomenology of OCD.

In a study by Salman Akhtar et al [26], it was found that the most common content of compulsions was dirt and contamination, similar to our study, followed by harm, symmetry, sexual and religious. However, this study did not talk about differences between male and female populations.

In a study conducted by Rajashekharaiyah M et al. [52] involving 50 Indian patients with Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) and using the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS), it was found that contamination was the most prevalent obsessional content, occurring in 60% of cases. Sexual content was observed in 26% of cases, while aggression and religious contents were each present in 24% of cases. The study also revealed that 42% of the patients had obsessions with a single content, whereas 58% had multiple contents.

Similarly, in our study, we found that 41.25% of cases had obsessions with a single content and 58.75% had multiple contents, with the nature of these obsessions being comparable.

In a 2001 study by Girishchandra BG et al. [53], 222 consecutive subjects were evaluated using the Yale-Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) symptom checklist and the Scale for Assessment of Form and Content (SFC). Factor analysis of the data revealed the main factors as washers, checkers, hoarding, and two pure obsession factors. The obsession groups predominantly exhibited sexual and religious themes. Given that Y-BOCS was used in this study and mental compulsions are categorized under the miscellaneous section, which is often overlooked in analyses, it is plausible that mental compulsions in these individuals may have been missed.

Prevalence of mental compulsions

The current study sought to examine the prevalence of mental compulsions and their associated clinical characteristics in a cross-sectional sample of adults with OCD. The prevalence of mental compulsions was 53.75%, which is comparable to the existing literature. 58.13 % of the participants endorsing mental compulsions were male, while 41.87% were female. Males had a higher prevalence of mental compulsions than females in our study, as mental compulsions were most common for religious or sexual obsessions which were present predominantly in males.

Similar findings regarding the prevalence of mental compulsions in OCD were observed in a study conducted in 2023 by Ferrão JVB et al [44]. The study aimed to evaluate the psychopathological correlates and prevalence of mental rituals in a large sample of OCD patients. By comparing 447 patients without mental rituals with 519 patients who had mental rituals, the researchers found that the lifetime prevalence of mental rituals was 55.4% and the current prevalence was 51.8%.

In 2017, T.S. Jaisoorya et al. [43] conducted a study to assess the prevalence and correlates of OCD and sub-threshold OCD among college students in Kerala, India and found that 57.4% of students with OCD had mental compulsions. However, this study did not discuss the kind of mental compulsions or their severity.

Similar results were also seen in a multicentric study conducted by Roseli G. Shavitt et al. [42] in 2014, to study the phenomenology of OCD, using DY-BOCS which asks about mental compulsions in each symptom dimension, the prevalence of mental compulsions was found to be 56.7% in patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder.

In a 2011 longitudinal study by Nicholas J. Sibrava et al. [41] involving 225 patients with Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD), it was found that 12.9% reported mental compulsions as their primary compulsion. Additionally, 20.4% indicated they were experiencing mental rituals at the time, though not as a major concern. Meanwhile, 16.0% reported having experienced mental rituals in the past but not currently, and 50.7% stated they had no history of mental rituals. Among the 29 individuals whose primary compulsion was mental rituals, only one (3.4%) acknowledged mental rituals as their sole obsessive symptom. Similar results were seen in our study, as we observed behavioural compulsions were present in most cases who endorsed mental compulsions. Only one case had only mental compulsions.

Phenomenology of mental compulsions

There are only limited studies that have reported on types of mental compulsions in patients with Obsessive – Compulsive Disorder. In this study, we found that the most common obsessions, overall, in patients with mental compulsions were about sacrilege and blasphemy (34.88%) followed by obsessions related to symmetry (32.55%), harm/aggression (27.0%) and sexual (25.58%). Most individuals had multiple mental compulsions (70%). The most common mental compulsions were undoing "bad" thoughts with "good" thoughts (51.2%) followed by praying (39.5%) and reassuring themselves (32.5%).

The most common obsessions in males with mental compulsions were about sacrilege and blasphemy followed by sexual. And most common mental compulsions were undoing “bad” thoughts with “good” thoughts (64%) and praying (48%), repeating phrases and mantras (24%), reassuring themselves (20%), counting numbers mentally (14%) and organising objects mentally (12%). The most common obsessions in females with mental compulsions were harm and symmetry and the most common mental compulsions were reassuring themselves (55.5%) and undoing bad thoughts with good thoughts (33.33%), praying (27.7%), counting numbers mentally (27.78%).

Similar findings were observed in a study by Roseli G Shavitt in 2014, [42] which found that mental compulsions were most common for symmetry/ordering/arranging e.g., organizing objects mentally; checking the list of tasks, aggression e.g., replacing bad/aggressive thoughts with good thoughts, and the sexual/religious dimensions e.g., thinking good thoughts after the thoughts that offended God; repeatedly praying in the mind to relieve the anxiety caused by intrusive sexual thoughts. Our study also found that mental compulsions were most common following sexual/religious dimensions and symmetry.

Sibrava et al. [41] conducted a study to evaluate the effects of primary mental rituals on clinical correlates, severity and chronicity in a large sample of OCD patients ($N = 225$) over a 4-year period. They found that the most commonly endorsed obsession was over-responsibility for harm, followed by thoughts of sacrilegiousness and fears of offending God. Our study also found that the most commonly endorsed obsession was sacrilege and blasphemous thoughts, followed by symmetry and then harm. And most common compulsions were replacing “bad” with “good” thoughts followed by praying which could be explained as religious and sexual obsessions were comparatively more common in this study.

Abramowitz et al in 2003 [30] conducted 2 studies in a large sample of 132 patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder to assess mental compulsions and found that mental compulsions were most prevalent among patients with intrusive religious/ blasphemous, aggressive, or sexual thoughts.

Our study is in accordance with previous studies suggesting mental compulsions are more common following religious, aggressive or sexual themes. However, there could be variations depending on socio-cultural background.

Comorbidities

Out of 80 participants, 58.75% ($n=47$) patients had a comorbid psychiatric illness and out of 43 patients with mental compulsions 60.46% ($n=26$) patients had any comorbid psychiatric illness. The most common associated comorbidity overall was depression (26.25%), generalised anxiety disorder (17.5%), any substance use (13.75%), and panic disorder (7.5%). Current alcohol use was seen in 10%, and current nicotine use was seen in 13.75%. Comorbidities were more in groups endorsing mental compulsions with depression being in

27.9% of individuals, generalised anxiety disorder in 20.9%, and panic disorder in 2.32 %. Current nicotine use was seen in 18.6%, and current alcohol use was seen in 11.62%.

In a chart review of comorbidity by Bhattacharya S, Reddy JC et al in 2005 [54], it was seen that 17% of 218 OCD participants had significant depression, 6% had dysthymia, and 7% had any anxiety condition. Except for the fact that female subjects were more likely to experience depression, the study showed little difference between the patients with comorbidity and those without.

However, there are no studies that discuss the differences in comorbidity in patients with mental compulsions and patients without mental compulsions

In an international collaboration [55] to explore cultural variations and the usefulness of the psychiatric diagnostic classification of obsessive-compulsive and related disorders, data was collected from multiple OCD treatment centres across seven countries and five continents. The study included a large and ethnically diverse sample of 3,711 adult patients with primary OCD from Brazil, India, Italy, South Africa, Japan, Australia, and Spain. The study reported on OCD comorbidity, age of onset of OCD and comorbid disorders, and suicidality. The findings revealed that the most prevalent comorbid disorders were major depressive disorder (28.4%), obsessive-compulsive personality disorder (24.5%), generalized anxiety disorder (19.3%), specific phobia (19.2%), and social phobia (18.5%).

Major depression was the most common lifetime co-occurring diagnosis, with a prevalence of 50.5%. Social phobia, specific phobia, and body dysmorphic disorder typically had an early age of onset. In contrast, co-occurring major depressive disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, and psychotic illnesses generally began later in life compared to OCD. Our study observed similar rates of comorbid depression and anxiety.

LIMITATIONS

- Sample size for the study was small.
- We could not determine whether mental compulsions or physical compulsions appeared first. Additionally, we did not assess how the symptom profile of mental compulsions evolved over time..
- Impact of treatment on the mental compulsion was not assessed.
- Any psychiatric diagnosis before the onset of mental compulsion OCD was not assessed.

STRENGTHS

- First kind of study in this part of the world.
- Both prevalence and impact of compulsion assessed by valid tools.
- Prevalence of common comorbidities in group with mental compulsions assessed.

CONCLUSIONS

- OCD is slightly more common in females than males in clinical sample. Onset occurs earlier in males than in females.
- Most common types of obsessions were dirt and contamination followed by symmetry, religious and harm/ aggression.
- Mental compulsions were present in more than half of the study sample.
- Mental compulsions were most common following religious, symmetry and harm related obsessions.
- Most of the patients had multiple mental compulsions
- Most common mental compulsions were undoing bad thoughts with good thoughts followed by praying, reassuring themselves and repeating phrases or mantras.
- Patients with mental compulsions had higher comorbid psychiatric illness than patients without mental compulsions. More than half of the sample had comorbid psychiatric illness

SUMMARY

1. This study was conducted to assess the prevalence, phenomenology and severity of mental compulsions in patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder.
2. This was a Cross-sectional, single center, interview-based study of total 80 study participants with diagnosis of OCD as per ICD-11, visiting psychiatry OPD of Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.
3. In our study, the age distribution among study participants was highest in 20-29 years age group and constituted 47.5% of the study population.
4. Our study had a slightly higher proportion of females compared to males, with females making up 51.2% of the sample and males 48.8%.
5. Mean age of the participants was 28.78 years (SD=8.9)
6. The mean age of onset of symptoms was 22.32 years (SD=5.6). The mean age of onset of symptoms in males was 21.2 years (SD=4.4) and in females was 23.4 years (SD=6.3).
7. Mean duration of illness was 6.31 years (SD=6.48). Median duration of illness was 5 years.
8. Out of 80 participants, 41.25% (n=33) had a single type of obsession and compulsion while 58.75% (n=47) had multiple types of obsessions and compulsions.
9. Most common obsessions and compulsions were in dimension of dirt and contamination i.e 48.75% (n=39) followed by symmetry – 27.5% (n=22), harm – 21.25% (n=17), religious – 21.25% (n=17) and sexual – 20% (n=16).
10. Out of 41 females, the most common obsessions and compulsions were in the dimension of dirt and contamination 56.09 (n=23) followed by symmetry 29.26% (n=12), harm 19.51% (n=8), miscellaneous compulsions 19.51% (n=8). Less commonly observed were religious 9.75% (n=4), sexual 7.31% (n=3), OCDs 7.31% (n=3) and collecting 2.43% (n=1).
11. Out of 39 males, the most common obsessions and compulsions were for dirt and contamination 41.02% (n=16) followed by religious 33.3% (n=13), sexual 33.3% (n=13), symmetry 25.6% (n=10). Less common were somatic 7.69% (n=3) and miscellaneous obsessions 5.12% (n=2).
12. Most participants (73.75%) had moderate to moderate-severe illness as per the YBOCS severity rating scale.

13. The overall point prevalence of mental compulsions in patients with Obsessive-compulsive disorder was 53.75% (n=43).
14. Mental compulsions were more common in males 58.13% (n=25) than in females 41.87% (n=18).
15. Most participants endorsed multiple compulsions, i.e. about 70% of participants had more than 1 mental compulsion.
16. 10 out of 80 patients i.e. 12.5% had mental compulsions as a primary compulsion in one of the domains. Out of 10, 5 had primary mental compulsions for harm obsessions, and 5 had primary mental compulsions for religious and sexual obsessions.
17. Only 1 patient had only mental compulsions and no behavioural compulsion and it was secondary to obsession that she might harm someone without meaning to harm them or blurt insults to someone and had mental compulsions in the form of replacing bad thoughts with good thoughts and reassuring herself.
18. Most commonly mental compulsions were associated with religious obsessions, 88% of patients with religious obsessions had mental compulsion. While 70.6 % of patients with harm obsessions, 68.75% of patients with sexual obsessions, 50% of patients with symmetry obsessions, and only 5% of patients with dirt and contamination obsessions.
19. Among 43 patients having mental compulsions, obsessions about sacrilege and blasphemy were most common (35%) followed by obsessions related to symmetry (32%). The most common mental compulsions were undoing “bad” thoughts with “good” thoughts (51%) followed by praying (40%) and reassuring themselves (32%).
20. Out of 80 patients, 47 (58.75%) patients had a comorbid psychiatric illness and out of 43 patients with mental compulsions 26 (60.46%) patients had any comorbid psychiatric illness. Overall, psychiatric comorbidity was more common in the participants with mental compulsions. 7.5 % of patients also reported suicidal ideations

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BLDE
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956
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The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 658/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "ASSESSMENT OF PREVALENCE AND PHENOMENOLOGY OF MENTAL COMPULSIONS IN PATIENT WITH OBSESSIVE-COMPULSIVE DISORDER: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. VARINDER PAL

NAME OF THE GUIDE: Dr. SANTOSH RAMDURG, Professor, Dept. of Psychiatry.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr. Akram A. Naikwad
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization.

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.

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INFORMED CONSENT

BLDE (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) SHRI. BM PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA-586103

INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN DISSERTATION/RESEARCH

I, the undersigned, _____, S/O D/O W/O _____, aged ____ years, ordinarily resident of _____ do hereby state/declare that Dr. VARINDER PAL of B.L.D.E.(DU)'S Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre have explained to me thoroughly on _____ at Vijayapura (place), and it has been explained to me in my own language that I have been diagnosed as having OBSESSIVE COMPULSIVE DISORDER. Further, DR. VARINDER PAL informed me that he is conducting a dissertation/research titled "ASSESSMENT OF PREVALENCE AND PHENOMENOLOGY OF MENTAL COMPULSIONS IN PATIENT OF OBSESSIVE COMPULSIVE DISORDER" under the guidance of Dr SANTOSH RAMDURG requesting my participation in the study. Besides routine treatment procedures, the study will use follow-up observations as reference data. Further Doctor has informed me that my participation in this study will help in the evaluation of the results of the study, which is a useful reference for the treatment of other similar cases in the near future.

The Doctor has also informed me that information given by me, observations made, photographs and video graphs taken upon me by the investigator will be confidential and not assessed by anyone other than me or my legal hirer except for academic purposes.

The Doctor did inform me that though my participation is purely voluntary, based on the information given by me, I can ask for any clarification during the course of treatment/study related to diagnosis, the procedure of treatment, result of treatment or prognosis. At the same time, I have been informed that I can withdraw from my participation in this study at any time if I want, or the investigator can terminate me from the study at any time from the study but not the procedure of treatment and follow-up unless I request to be discharged.

After understanding the nature of dissertation or research, diagnosis made, mode of treatment, I the undersigned Shri/Smt _____ under my full conscious state of mind agree to participate in the said research/ dissertation.

Signature of the patient:

Signature of Doctor:

Witness: 1.

Date

Place

PROFORMA

BLDE(DU.)'S SHRI. BM PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.

Name:

Age:

Sex:

Religion:

Occupation:

Education:

Socioeconomic status:

Residence:

Address and Mobile number:

Chief complaints:

Age at the onset of symptoms :

Duration after which patient first sought medical help :

History of treatment, if any :

ASSESSMENT PROTOCOL

DIMENSIONAL YALE-BROWN OBSESSIVE COMPULSIVE SCALE SYMPTOM
CHECKLIST

YALE-BROWN OBSESSIVE COMPULSIVE SCALE (YBOCS.)

GLOBAL ASSESSMENT OF FUNCTIONING

Part I: Obsessive-Compulsive Symptom Checklist

We ask that you please complete the entire checklist that follows.

When completing this questionnaire, please consider the following definitions:

Obsessions are upsetting repetitive and intrusive thoughts or images. Examples include a recurring concern about whether a light has been switched off or a door has been locked. Other examples include worries about germs and diseases. These thoughts or images continue even when the person tries to ignore or suppress them.

Compulsions are repetitive acts, behaviors or mental rituals that the person feels he or she has to perform. For example, repeated checking that the door is locked or appliances are off. Other examples include repetitive hand washing or the need to place things in a certain order.

Please check ✓ one or more boxes in each row as appropriate ("past" means that the symptom was present in the past but not during the previous week). If a symptom has ever been present (current or past), please indicate the age of onset. For children, parents should complete this form with the help of their child.

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Obsessions about Harm and Related Compulsions
				1. I have obsessions that I might harm myself. For example, fear of hurting myself with a knife or fork, fear of handling or being near sharp objects, fear of jumping in front of a car, or a fear of walking near glass windows.
				2. I have obsessions that I will be harmed. For example, a fear of being hurt because I am not careful enough. Fear that people or certain objects will harm me.
				3. I check that I did not harm myself or was not harmed. For example, looking for injuries or bleeding after handling sharp or breakable objects or checking with doctors or others for reassurance that you haven't hurt yourself.
				4. I have obsessions that I might harm other people. For example, fear of poisoning other people's food, fear of harming babies, fear of pushing someone in front of a car or train.
				5. I have obsessions that I will harm other people without meaning to hurt them. Worries about being involved in a hit-and-run car accident, fear of being responsible by not providing assistance for some imagined catastrophe, fear of hurting someone's feelings, fear of causing harm by giving wrong advice.
				6. I have obsessions that I may be responsible for something else terrible happening. For example, fear of starting up a fire or being responsible for a burglary or a murder.
				7. I check that I did not harm others or that others were not harmed. For example, checking that you haven't hurt someone without knowing it. You may ask others for reassurance, or telephone to make sure that everything is all right.

				<p>8. I have violent or horrific images in my mind. For example, images of murders or accidents or other gory images such as dismembered bodies.</p>
				<p>9. I have obsessions that I might blurt out obscenities or insults. For example, a fear of shouting obscenities in a quiet place with many people around - like a church or in a classroom. A fear of writing obscenities.</p>
				<p>10. I have obsessions that involve doing something else embarrassing. For example, fear of taking off my clothes in public or appearing foolish in social situations.</p>
				<p>11. I obsess about acting on an unwanted impulse. A fear of stabbing a friend or driving car into a tree or a fear of running someone over <i>on impulse</i>. Fear that you may steal things.</p>
				<p>12. I check that nothing terrible will or did happen. For example, searching the newspaper or listening to the radio or television for news about some catastrophe you believe you caused. You may also ask people for reassurance.</p>
				<p>13. I check or take other measures to prevent or avoid harm coming to myself or others. For example, you may stay away from sharp or breakable objects. You may refuse to handle knives or scissors, and you may avoid fragile glass objects. You may ask others for reassurance or ask them to be with you to make sure that harmful things don't happen.</p>
				<p>14. I need to repeat routine activities to prevent terrible consequences. For example, needing to do the same action over and over again after having a "bad," obsessive thoughts about harmful acts - in order to prevent some terrible consequence. Please check this item only if the repeating is done in response to harmful thoughts.</p>
				<p>15. I have mental rituals other than checking. For example, mental rituals are compulsions you do "in your head", like thinking of a "good" thought to undo a "bad" thought or needing to keep mental lists that have to be remembered in a certain order. . Please check this item only if these mental rituals are specifically related to or done in order to relieve obsessions about harming yourself or others.</p>

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	
Sexual and Religious Obsessions and Related Compulsions				
				<p>16. I have forbidden or improper sexual thoughts, images, or impulses. For example, unwanted sexual thoughts about strangers, family, or friends.</p>
				<p>17. I have sexual obsessions that involve children or incest. For example, unwanted thoughts about sexually molesting either your own or other children.</p>
				<p>18. I have obsessions about homosexuality. For example, worries like "Am I a homosexual" or "What if I suddenly become gay?" when there is no basis for this concern.</p>

				<p>19. I have obsessions about violent sexual behavior towards other people. For example, unwanted images of violent sexual behavior toward adult strangers, friends, or family members.</p>
				<p>20. I check to make sure that I have not done anything wrong of a sexual nature. For example, checking your private parts, bedding, or clothing for evidence of wrong doing. Asking for reassurance that nothing bad has happened.</p>
				<p>21. I avoid certain actions, people, places or things to prevent sexual obsessions and compulsions from occurring. For example, not going into the magazine section of a bookstore because of some of the pictures or titles.</p>
				<p>22. I am obsessed with sacrilege and blasphemy. For example, worries about having blasphemous thoughts, saying evil things or being punished for these things.</p>
				<p>23. I am obsessed with what is really right or wrong in a moral sense. For example, worries about always doing things in the morally correct way or worries about having told a lie or having cheated someone.</p>
				<p>24. I fear saying certain things. For example, fear of saying something awful or inappropriate that might be considered disrespectful to someone living or dead. Some people have a fearful of giving the wrong advice.</p>
				<p>25. I check to make sure that I have not done anything wrong of a religious nature. For example, checking your Bible or other scared objects. Or asking for reassurance that nothing has happened from your priest, rabbi, or minister.</p>
				<p>26. I have compulsions that involve religious duties or objects. For example, excessive cleaning or checking of religious objects. Praying for hours at a time or seeking reassurance from religious leaders more often than is really necessary.</p>
				<p>27. I avoid certain actions, people, places or things to prevent obsessions and compulsions about religion or morality from occurring. For example, not going to church or not watching certain TV shows because they may provoke thoughts of being possessed by an evil influence or the devil.</p>
				<p>28. I need to repeat routine activities to prevent terrible consequences. For example, needing to do the same action over and over again after having a "bad," sexual or religious obsessional thought) in order prevent some terrible consequence. Please don't endorse this symptom unless the repeating is in response to such thoughts.</p>
				<p>29. I need to tell, ask or confess things. For example, asking other people to reassure you about possible wrongdoing; confessing to a wrong thing that didn't occur or telling people your private thoughts to feel better.</p>
				<p>30. I have mental rituals other than checking. For example, mental rituals are compulsions you do "in your head", like thinking of a "good" thought to undo a "bad" thought or needing to keep mental lists that have to be remembered in a certain order. . Please check this item only if these mental rituals are specifically related to or done in order to relieve sexual or religious obsessions.</p>

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Ordering, Symmetry, Counting, Doing and Re-doing and the Need for Things to be "Just Right"
				31. I have obsessions about things needing to be perfect or exact. For example, worries or uncomfortable feelings about papers and books being properly aligned, worries about calculations being done perfectly or my handwriting being perfect.
				32. I have obsessions about symmetry. For example, being totally obsessed or preoccupied if certain sensations, thoughts, or things are not even or symmetrical
				33. I check that I did not make mistakes. For example, repeated checking while reading, writing, or doing simple calculations to make sure you didn't make a mistake. Checking lists. This may involve making lists of things to do and obsessively checking these lists.
				34. I re-read or re-write things. For example, you may take hours to read a few pages in a book or to write a short letter because you get stuck in a cycle of reading and re-reading. This may also involve searching for a "perfect" word or phrase, or worry that you didn't really understand the meaning of what you read, or having obsessions about the shape of certain letters.
				35. I need to repeat routine activities (like going in and out of a doorway or getting up and down from a chair). Other examples include repeating routine activities like turning appliances on and off, setting an object down on a table, combing your hair, or looking in a particular direction. You may not feel comfortable unless you do these things the "right" number of times or so that a certain evenness or symmetry has been achieved. Try to distinguish this one from doing things over and over to get rid of a bad thought or an obsession.
				36. I have counting compulsions. For example, counting objects like ceiling or floor tiles, books in a bookcase, nails in a wall, or even grains of sand on the beach.
				37. I have ordering or arranging compulsions. For example, straightening paper and pens on a desktop or books in a bookcase. You may waste hours arranging things in your house just so, and you may become very upset if this order is disturbed.
				38. I have compulsions that involve symmetrical touching or evening- up movements or things. For example, if I touch or do something on the right side, I need to do touch or do the same thing on the left side.
				39. I need to touch, tap, or rub things. For example, you may feel the urge to touch rough surfaces like wood, or hot surfaces like a stovetop. Feeling the urge to lightly touch other people. Feeling the urge to touch an object. Needing to rub or pick at things.
				40. I fear not saying "just the right thing". For example, you may feel that you need to find "just the right" word or phrase before saying something or answering someone.

				<p>41. I have mental rituals other than checking or evening-up. For example, mental rituals are compulsions you do "in your head." Please check this item only if these mental rituals are specifically related to obsessions of symmetry, exactness, or just right perceptions.</p>
				<p>42. I avoid certain actions, people, places or things to prevent obsessions and compulsions about symmetry or exactness from occurring. For example, not looking at certain things in the house because they are sure to prompt obsessions or compulsions.</p>

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Contamination Worries & Cleaning Compulsions
				<p>43. I am obsessed with dirt or germs. For example getting germs from sitting in certain chairs, shaking hands, or touching door handles.</p>
				<p>44. I am overly concerned or disgusted with bodily waste or secretions (like urine, feces, or saliva). For example fears of being on contact with one's own or someone else's urine, feces, semen, or vaginal secretions.</p>
				<p>45. I am obsessed with environmental contaminants (like asbestos, radiation, or toxic waste). For example, fear of being contaminated by asbestos or radon, fear of radioactive substances, fear of things associated with towns containing toxic waste sites. Fear of being contaminated by pollution.</p>
				<p>46. I have obsessions about insects or animals. For example, fear of being contaminated by flies by being in contact with a dog, cat, or other animals.</p>
				<p>47. I am bothered by sticky substances or residues. For example, fear of adhesive tape, sap, tooth paste or other sticky substances that may trap contaminants.</p>
				<p>48. I am concerned I will get ill because of contamination. For example, fear of becoming ill as a direct result of being contaminated. This may include fears of contracting specific diseases such as AIDS or cancer specifically because of contamination.</p>
				<p>49. I have compulsive or ritualized handwashing. For example, needing to wash and rewash your hands because of worries about dirt or germs or because you don't feel your hands are clean enough. Often if the sequence of washing is interrupted, the whole process may have to be restarted. The ritual may involve needing to wash your hands a certain number of times or in certain ways.</p>
				<p>50. I have compulsive or ritualized showering, bathing, or toilet routines. For example, your showers, baths, and other bathroom routines may have to be done in a certain order. You may use an excessive amount of toilet tissue. Often if the sequence of washing or cleaning is interrupted, the whole process may have to be restarted.</p>

				<p>51. I have compulsions that involve repeated cleaning of household items or other inanimate objects. For example, excessive and/or repetitive cleaning of faucets, toilets, floors, kitchen counters, or kitchen utensils.</p>
				<p>52. I do other things to prevent or remove contact with contaminants. For example, asking family members remove insecticides, garbage, gasoline cans, raw meat, paints, varnish, drugs in the medicine cabinet, or kitty litter, if you can't avoid these things. Or you might use rubber gloves</p>
				<p>53. I have mental rituals other than checking. For example, mental rituals are compulsions you do "in your head." Please check this item only if these mental rituals are specifically related to contamination worries.</p>
				<p>54. I avoid doing certain things or going to certain places because of contamination concerns. For example, not going to public restrooms, not using hotel towels, or not shaking hands. You may ask family members to open doors or you may wear gloves, or use Kleenex or paper towels to avoid touching things directly.</p>

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Collecting and Hoarding
				<p>55. I have obsessions about needing to save or hoard things for the future. For example, worries about throwing things away (papers, documents, ticket stubs) because you might need them in the future.</p>
				<p>56. I have obsessions about discarding things. For example, keeping lots of things because of their sentimental value, or because of an urge to pick up or collect things.</p>
				<p>57. I have obsessions about losing things. For example, worries about losing a trinket, or unimportant objects like a scrap of paper.</p>
				<p>58. I having difficulty deciding whether or not I should save something. For example, I will pick up something for no reason and keep because I can't decide to throw it away.</p>
				<p>59. I have compulsions to hoard or collect things. For example, I may have rooms filled with old newspapers, notes, cans, paper towels, wrappers and empty bottles - I don't throw these things away because I fear that I may one day need them. I may also pick up objects or trash from the street or from garbage cans.</p>
				<p>60. I have mental rituals that concern hoarding or saving things. For example, mental rituals are compulsions I do "in my head", like thinking of a "good" thought to undo a "bad" thought or needing to keep mental lists that have to be remembered in a certain order. (Please check this item only if these mental rituals are specifically related to <i>hoarding</i> obsessions.)</p>
				<p>61. I avoid certain actions, people, places or things to prevent hoarding compulsions. For example, not walking past certain stores or markets, or not reading the newspaper. Asking other people to clean up my closet and throw things away.</p>

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Somatic Obsessions & Compulsions
				62. I am concerned with illness or disease. For example, worries about having an illness like cancer, heart disease, AIDS, despite reassurance from doctors.
				63. I have checking rituals related to obsessions about disease or illness. For example, seeking reassurance from friends or doctors that I don't have a serious illness like heart disease, or a brain tumor or some other form of cancer. I may repeatedly check a body part or compulsively take my pulse, blood pressure, or temperature.
				64. I have mental rituals other than checking. For example, mental rituals are compulsions I do "in my head." Please check this item only if these mental rituals are specifically related to somatic worries
				65. I avoid certain actions, people, places or things to prevent obsessions and compulsions about disease from occurring. For example, not driving past a hospital because it will provoke thoughts of illness.

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Miscellaneous Obsessions & Compulsions
				66. I need to know or remember certain things. For example, needing to remember insignificant things like license plate numbers, bumper stickers or T-shirt slogans.
				67. I have superstitious fears. For example, a fear of passing a cemetery, hearse, a black cat, walking under a ladder, breaking a mirror or fear of omens associated with death.
				68. I have superstitious behaviors. For example, I may not take a bus or train if its number contains an "unlucky" number like thirteen. I may be reluctant to leave your house on the thirteenth of the month. I may throw away clothes you wore while passing a funeral home or cemetery.
				69. I have lucky or unlucky numbers. For example, worries about common numbers like thirteen, having to do activities a certain "lucky" number of times, or having to start an activity only at a certain lucky hour of the day. Also this might involve avoiding numbers that could bring bad luck.
				70. I have obsessions and/or compulsions about colors with special significance. For example, black may be associated with death, red may be associated with blood and injury. You may avoid using objects of these colors.

				<p>71. Intrusive nonsense sounds, names, words, or music come into my mind. For example, hearing words, songs or music in my mind that I can't stop. Getting stuck on the sound of certain names or words.</p>
				<p>72. Intrusive nonviolent images come into my mind. For example, imaging neutral scenes. Getting stuck on the visual details of certain pictures of scenes.</p>
				<p>73. I avoid certain actions, people, places or things to prevent any of these miscellaneous obsessions and compulsions. For example, not walking on cracks or not writing certain numbers.</p>
				<p>74. I get stuck doing routine behaviors and it slows me down. For example, showering or getting dressed or going out of the house can take hours. Others may get stuck eating or talking so that these everyday activities take much longer than necessary to perform.</p>
				<p>75. I make lists much more than I need to. I make many lists of things to do or check.</p>

Never	Current (Past week)	Past	Age of Onset	Other OC Spectrum Obsessions & Compulsions
				<p>76. I obsess about the possibility of being separated from a close family member. For example, worrying that something terrible might happen to a parent or child or lover that would result in never seeing them again.</p>
				<p>77. I have compulsions or rituals that are done in order to prevent the loss of someone (or being separated from someone) very important to me. For example, following that special person from room to room or calling them over and over again on the telephone; having to pray or doing specific rituals in order to avoid that bad things happen to someone.</p>
				<p>78. I am obsessed that I might become a particular person. For example, having the thought that I might become like a particular person or even become that other person; fear that one part of my body does not belong to me.</p>
				<p>79. I have compulsions to rid myself of thinking so much about another person I am obsessed by. For example, pushing the unwanted thoughts away or performing some other ritual to get rid of those thoughts.</p>
				<p>80. I have staring rituals. For example, needing to look at things so that their edges line-up just right or having to look at things in a certain way for a certain time.</p>
				<p>81. I have the urge to repeat something that I or someone else has said. This might be a certain word you can't get out of your mind or it might be the end of phrase that you just said or heard someone else say.</p>

				<p>82. I am excessively concerned with a part of my body or an aspect of my appearance. For example, worries about the appearance, safety or functioning that your face, ears, nose, eyes, or other part of your body. Worries that some part of your body is misshapen or ugly, despite being told you look OK.</p>
				<p>83. I check something related to obsessions about my appearance. For example, seeking reassurance from friends about your appearance. Repeatedly checking yourself for body odors or check your appearance (facial features or other physical features) by looking in a mirror for ugly features. Needing to groom yourself continuously or compare some aspect of your body to other people; you may have to wear certain clothes on certain days. Being obsessed with your weight.</p>
				<p>84. I have obsessions about food. For example, being obsessed with recipes, calories, and/or dieting.</p>
				<p>85. I have obsessions and/or compulsions about physical exercise. For example, being obsessed with the need for exercise to burn off calories. Related compulsions include exercising according to certain rules or for a certain duration of time.</p>
				<p>86. I have eating rituals. You may have to arrange your food, knife, and fork in a particular order before eating. You may have to eat according to a strict ritual, or may not be able to eat until the hands of a clock are exactly on a certain time.</p>
				<p>87. I pull my hair out (obsessions and compulsions). For example, you may pull your hair from your scalp, eyelids, eyelashes, or pubic areas. You may use your fingers or tweezers to pull your hair. Typically this involves seeking the right hair. You may visually inspect the hair or do something else (remove the follicle or bite the hair). You may produce bald spots on your scalp that require a wig, or pluck your eyelids or eyebrows smooth.</p>
				<p>88. I pick at my skin (obsessions and compulsions). For example, you may pick at the skin around your fingernails, bumps on your skin or near sores. You may injure yourself or make the sores worse.</p>

Yale Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) Part 2

Thank you for completing the Y-BOCS checklist. Please circle the most upsetting obsessions and compulsions that you currently experience. Remember the definitions of obsessions and compulsions and the examples of each that you may have noted on the checklist, and place a check mark by the appropriate number from 0-4 under each question below.

OBSESSIVE THOUGHTS: Review the obsessions you checked on the Y-BOCS Symptom Checklist to help you answer the first five questions. Please think about the times when these symptoms were at their worst in the last 3-6 months (including today), and check one answer for each question.

1. TIME OCCUPIED BY OBSESSIVE THOUGHTS How much of your time was occupied by obsessive thoughts? How frequently did these thoughts occur?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	None
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	Less than 1 hour per day, or occasional intrusions (occur no more than 8 times a day)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	1-3 hours per day, or frequent intrusions (most hours of the day are free of obsessions)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	More than 3 hours and up to 8 hours per day, or very frequent intrusions
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	More than 8 hours per day, or near-constant intrusions

2. INTERFERENCE DUE TO OBSESSIVE THOUGHTS: How much did these thoughts interfere with your social or work functioning? Is there anything that you didn't do because of them?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	No interference
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	Mild, slight interference with social or occupational performance, but still performance not impaired
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	Moderate, definitive interference with social or occupational performance, but still manageable
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	Severe interference, causes substantial impairment in social or occupational performance
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	Extreme, incapacitating interference

3. DISTRESS ASSOCIATED WITH OBSESSIVE THOUGHTS How much distress did your obsessive thoughts cause you?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	None
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	Mild, infrequent, and not too disturbing distress
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	Moderate, frequent, and disturbing distress, but still manageable
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	Severe, very frequent, and very disturbing distress
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	Extreme, near-constant, and disabling distress

4. RESISTANCE AGAINST OBSESSIONS		
How much effort did you make to resist the obsessive thoughts? How often did you try to disregard or turn your attention away from those thoughts as they entered your mind?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	I made an effort to always resist (or the obsessions are so minimal that there is no need to actively resist them)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	I tried to resist most of the time (e.g. more than half the time I tried to resist)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	I made some effort to resist
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	I allowed all obsessions to fill my mind without attempting to control them, but I did so with some reluctance
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	I completely and willingly gave in to all obsessions

5. DEGREES OF CONTROL OVER OBSESSIVE THOUGHTS		
How much control did you have over your obsessive thoughts? How successful were you in stopping or diverting your obsessive thinking?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	Complete control
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	Much control; usually I could stop or divert obsessions with some effort and concentration
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	Moderate control; sometimes I could stop or divert obsessions
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	Little control; I was rarely successful in stopping obsessions and could only divert attention with great difficulty
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	No control; I was rarely able to even momentarily ignore the obsessions

	OBSESSION SUBTOTAL (Add items 1-5)
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COMPULSIONS: Review the compulsions you checked on the Y-BOCS Symptom Checklist to help you answer these five questions. Please think about the times when these symptoms were at their worst in the last 3-6 months (including today), and check one answer for each question.

6. TIME SPENT PERFORMING COMPULSIVE BEHAVIORS		
How much time did you spend performing compulsive behaviors? How frequently did you perform compulsions?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	None
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	Less than 1 hour per day was spent performing compulsions, or occasional performance of compulsive behaviors (no more than 8 times per day)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	1-3 hours per day was spent performing compulsions, or frequent performance of compulsive behaviors (most hours were free of compulsions)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	More than 3 hours and up to 8 hours per day were spent performing compulsions, or very frequent performance of compulsive behaviors (during most hours of the day)
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	More than 8 hours were spent performing compulsions, or near-constant performance of compulsive behaviors (hour rarely passes without several compulsions being performed)

7. INTERFERENCE DUE TO COMPULSIVE BEHAVIORS		
How much did your compulsive behaviors interfere with your social or work functioning?		
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 =	No interference
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 =	Mild, slight interference with social or occupational activities, but overall performance not impaired
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 =	Moderate, definite interference with social or occupational performance, but still manageable
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 =	Severe interference, substantial impairment in social or occupational performance
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 =	Extreme, incapacitating interference

8. DISTRESS ASSOCIATED WITH COMPULSIVE BEHAVIORS	
How would you have felt if prevented from performing your compulsions? How anxious would you have become?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 = Not at all anxious
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 = Only slightly anxious if compulsions prevented
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 = Anxiety would mount but remain manageable if compulsions prevented
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 = Prominent and very disturbing increase in anxiety if compulsions interrupted
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 = Extreme, incapacitating anxiety from any intervention aimed at reducing the compulsions

9. RESISTANCE	
How much effort did you make to resist the compulsions? Or how often did you try to stop the compulsions?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 = I made effort to always resist (or the symptoms were so minimal that there was no need to actively resist them)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 = I tried to resist most of the time (e.g. more than half the time)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 = I made some effort to resist
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 = I yielded to almost all compulsions without attempting to control them, but I did so with some reluctance
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 = I completely and willingly yielded to all compulsions

10. DEGREES OF CONTROL OVER COMPULSIVE BEHAVIORS	
How much control did you have over the compulsive behaviors? How successful were you in stopping the ritual(s)?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 = I had complete control
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 = Usually I could stop compulsions or rituals with some effort and willpower
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 = Sometimes I could stop compulsive behaviors, but only with difficulty
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 = I could only delay the compulsive behaviors, but eventually they had to be carried out to completion
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 = I was rarely able to even momentarily delay performing the compulsive behaviors

	COMPULSIVE SUBTOTAL (Add items 6-10)
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11. Do you think your obsessions or compulsions are reasonable or rational? Would there be anything besides anxiety to worry about if you resisted them? Do you think something would really happen?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	0 = I think my obsessions or compulsions are unreasonable or excessive
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 = I think my obsessions or compulsions are unreasonable or excessive, but I'm not completely convinced that they aren't necessary
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 = I think my obsessions or compulsions may be unreasonable or excessive
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 = I don't think my obsessions or compulsions are unreasonable or excessive
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 = I am sure my obsessions or compulsions are reasonable, no matter what anyone says

Global Assessment of Functioning (GAF) Scale

(From DSM-IV-TR, p. 34.)

Consider psychological, social, and occupational functioning on a hypothetical continuum of mental health-illness. Do not include impairment in functioning due to physical (or environmental) limitations.

Code	(Note: Use intermediate codes when appropriate, e.g., 45, 68, 72.)
100 91	Superior functioning in a wide range of activities, life's problems never seem to get out of hand, is sought out by others because of his or her many positive qualities. No symptoms.
90 81	Absent or minimal symptoms (e.g., mild anxiety before an exam), good functioning in all areas, interested and involved in a wide range of activities, socially effective, generally satisfied with life, no more than everyday problems or concerns (e.g. an occasional argument with family members).
80 71	If symptoms are present, they are transient and expectable reactions to psychosocial stressors (e.g., difficulty concentrating after family argument); no more than slight impairment in social, occupational or school functioning (e.g., temporarily failing behind in schoolwork).
70 61	Some mild symptoms (e.g. depressed mood and mild insomnia) OR some difficulty in social, occupational, or school functioning (e.g., occasional truancy, or theft within the household), but generally functioning pretty well, has some meaningful interpersonal relationships.
60 51	Moderate symptoms (e.g., flat affect and circumstantial speech, occasional panic attacks) OR moderate difficulty in social, occupational, or school functioning (e.g., few friends, conflicts with peers or co-workers).
50 41	Serious symptoms (e.g., suicidal ideation, severe obsessional rituals, frequent shoplifting) OR any serious impairment in social, occupational, or school functioning (e.g., no friends, unable to keep a job).
40 31	Some impairment in reality testing or communication (e.g., speech is at times illogical, obscure, or irrelevant) OR major impairment in several areas, such as work or school, family relations, judgment, thinking, or mood (e.g., depressed man avoids friends, neglects family, and is unable to work; child frequently beats up younger children, is defiant at home, and is failing at school).
30 21	Behavior is considerably influenced by delusions or hallucinations OR serious impairment in communication or judgment (e.g., sometimes incoherent, acts grossly inappropriately, suicidal preoccupation) OR inability to function in almost all areas (e.g., stays in bed all day; no job, home, or friends).
20 11	Some danger of hurting self or others (e.g., suicide attempts without clear expectation of death; frequently violent; manic excitement) OR occasionally fails to maintain minimal personal hygiene (e.g., smears feces) OR gross impairment in communication (e.g., largely incoherent or mute).
10 1	Persistent danger of severely hurting self or others (e.g., recurrent violence) OR persistent inability to maintain minimal personal hygiene OR serious suicidal act with clear expectation of death.
0	Inadequate information.

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